

MONITORING THE MIGRATION OF THE DANUBE SHAD (*ALOSA IMMACULATA*) FROM KM 615 (GÂRCOV) TO KM 863 (IRON GATES II) AND THE INFLUENCE OF HYDROCLIMATIC FACTORS

Mioara COSTACHE, Nino MARICA, Mihail COSTACHE, Silvia RADU, Nicoleta
Georgeta DOBROTĂ, Gheorghe DOBROTĂ

RESEARCH – DEVELOPMENT STATION FOR FISHERIES NUCET

Address: Principală, no. 549, postal code: 137335 Dâmbovița Tel/Fax: +40245267003

e-mail: scp_nucet@yahoo.com Web page: www.statiuneapiscicolanucet.ro

SUMMARY

*The paper presents the results of research on monitoring the migration of the Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) on the Danube sector between km 615 (Gârcov) and km 863 (Iron Gates II), with an emphasis on the influence of hydroclimatic factors. The Danube shad is an anadromous migratory species of great ecological and economic value that carries out its life cycle between the Black Sea and the river, where it reproduces. Its migration is strongly conditioned by factors such as water temperature, the flow and level of the Danube, turbidity and chemical composition of the water. Physico-chemical and hydrobiological analyses of the water revealed a suitable quality for reproduction. The structure of the phytoplankton and zooplankton indicated a moderate specific diversity, dominated by Bacillariophyta and Rotifera. The study involved experimental fishing and the collection of 208 specimens, analyzed morphologically, biometrically and according to age and sex. The results showed the predominance of 3 and 4 year old specimens, with gonads in stages IV and IV-V, confirming spawning in portions. Prolificity increased with age and gonad stage. The conclusions emphasize the need to correlate environmental regulations with exploitation regulations to ensure sustainable management of shad stocks, in the context of pressures generated by the presence of the Iron Gates dam, overfishing and climate change.*

Keywords: *Danube shad, migration, hydroclimatic factors.*

INTRODUCTION

The Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) is an important species in the Danube-Danube Delta-Black Sea ecological system and has a high economic value due to the large quantities caught and the taste qualities appreciated by the population in the lower Danube area [5]. Knowledge of the essential elements regarding the biology and exploitation of the species contributes to providing basic information for the conservation of the species and the management of stocks. The development of the life cycle in two environments (freshwater and marine), located at great distances in different periods of time, requires knowledge and updating of the impact of new environmental conditions on the population [4]. Knowledge of the migration of adults for reproduction and the return of juveniles to the sea under the pressure of environmental factors can be used in the development of stock management tactics. Environmental regulations must be associated with exploitation ones so that the

biological and socio-economic objectives of the Danube shad fishery can be achieved harmoniously.

The Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*), figure no. 1, is a migratory fish species of the Clupeidae family, adapted to both marine and freshwater life. It has great ecological and economic importance, being one of the most valuable migratory fish species in the Danube ecosystem [1].

Figure 1. Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*)

Biology of the Danube shad

a). Morphology and general characteristics

- **Size:** 25 - 40 cm long, can reach up to 50 cm;
- **Weight:** 300 - 600 g, but can exceed 1 kg;
- **Appearance:** Fusiform body, laterally compressed, covered with silvery scales;
- **Head and mouth:** Small head, large mouth, lacking obvious teeth;
- **Coloration:** Blue-green back, silvery abdomen and flanks.

b). Life cycle and reproduction

- **Longevity:** 5 - 6 years;
- **Sexual maturity:** at 2 - 4 years, depending on environmental conditions;
- **Reproduction:**
 - anadromous species – migrates from the Black Sea to the Danube for reproduction;
 - spawns in freshwater, in areas with moderate current and sandy or rocky substrate;
 - fecundity: between 30,000 and 120,000 eggs per female.

After spawning, the adults return to the Black Sea, and the fry remain in the Danube for a period of time before migrating to the sea.

Ecology of the Danube shad

a). Habitat and distribution

- It lives mainly in the Black Sea, in coastal areas and in brackish waters;
- Migrates to the Danube and tributaries for reproduction, ascending to the Iron Gates;
- It prefers clean, well-oxygenated waters, with temperatures between 12 - 18° C during the breeding period.

b). Feeding

- in the sea: planktonic feeding – consumes zooplankton, small crustaceans, fish larvae.
- in freshwater: it feeds less, food consumption is reduced during the breeding season.

c). Ecological role

- contributes to the balance of aquatic ecosystems through its migrations, influencing the food chain.
- can be consumed by ichthyophagous birds and predatory fish species (pike perch, catfish, etc.).
- serves as an indicator of water quality, being sensitive to pollution.

d). Limiting factors of migration and conservation of Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*)

- The construction of dams, for example, the Iron Gates, has limited the breeding range;
- Overfishing and poaching are putting pressure on fish stocks.
- Pollution and climate change, especially global warming, affect reproductive success.

General data on the migration of Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*)

Fish migration is an essential phenomenon for the maintenance of aquatic ecosystems and the perpetuation of species. The Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) is an anadromous migratory fish, which means that it lives in the sea but migrates to the river to reproduce. Knowledge of adult migration for reproduction and the return of juveniles to the sea under the pressure of environmental factors can be used in the development of stock management tactics [2, 3].

The migration of Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) from the Black Sea to the Danube River for reproduction is influenced by a number of essential hydrological factors. These include [6, 7, 8]:

- water temperature

One of the main triggers for migration is rising water temperatures. The peak of migration usually occurs in the second decade of April and the first decade of May, when water temperatures reach values between 9 and 17° C.

- water level and flow rate

Changes in the level and flow of the Danube influence the accessibility and migration conditions for shad. Rising water levels can facilitate the fish's access to breeding grounds, while sudden fluctuations can represent obstacles to migration.

- water turbidity

The degree of turbidity can affect the migratory behavior of shad. More turbid waters can provide protection against predators, but excessive turbidity can negatively influence the orientation and migratory ability of the fish.

- water chemistry

The chemical composition of the water, including dissolved oxygen concentrations and the presence of pollutants, can influence the health and behavior of shad during migration.

These environmental factors play a crucial role in the development of the Danube shad migration, influencing both the timing of its onset and the efficiency of the reproductive process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research methods

Data collection on Danube shad migration

To collect data on the migration of Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) schools in the Danube sector from Km 615 (Gârcov) to Km 863 (Iron Gates II), a multidisciplinary approach was used, combining fauna monitoring techniques, ecological studies and community involvement, by following certain essential steps in this process, namely:

a). Preliminary studies

- Identification of the distribution area of the Danube shad and its preferred habitats.

- Study of the bibliography regarding the migration of the species.
- b). Field data collection through:
 - Organizing expeditions for direct observation of migration;
 - Capturing batches, determining the age and performing biometric measurements of the specimens and establishing the prolificity and maturation stage of the females;
- c). Collection of data on hydroclimatic factors in the area of the Danube sector offrom Km 615 (Gârcov) to Km 863 (Iron Gates II);
- d). Monitoring of the physical and chemical parameters of the Danube water in the areafrom Km 615 (Gârcov) to Km 863 (Iron Gates II)
- e). Monitoring of the hydrobiological parameters of the Danube water in the area from Km 615 (Gârcov) to Km 863 (Iron Gates II)
- f). Presentation and analysis of data on research conducted in 2025 on the migration of Danube shad (*Alosa immacuata*)in the sector Km 615 (Gârcov) to Km 863 (Iron Gates II)

Monitoring techniques used

To achieve the proposed objectives, the ichthyological material was collected in the spring (May 2025) in the sector km 615 (Gârcov) to km 863 (Iron Gates II). The ichthyological samples were taken through experimental fishing using floating nets with mesh sizes from 30 x 30 mm to 40 x 40 mm, the set length being 100 m to 200 m, and the set width being 4 - 6 m. The nets were with and without a gillnet. The fishing technique used is schematically shown in table no. 1.

Table no. 1. Fishing technique used

No. No.	Fishing technique	Duration (minutes)
1.	Preparing the tools	10 - 20
2.	Travel to the launch site	10 - 40
3.	Launching tools	10 - 15
4.	The actual floating	30 - 40
5.	Removing tools	15 - 25
6.	Untangling the fish	10 - 15
7.	Returning the boat to the fishing spot	10 - 20
8.	Time of fishing (day/night)	day

In figure no. 2 experimental fishing using nets, and in figure no. 3 the untangling of fish from fishing gear (nets), examples of Danube shad caught during experimental fishing.

Figure 2. Experimental fishing using nets

Figure 3. Disengaging fish from fishing gear

To cover the migration of shad in time and space samples were extracted from the commercial catches of fishermen. The age, sex, body mass and morphological parameters of the captured fish specimens (208 specimens) were determined. The collection, fixation, processing and determination of the ichthyological material was carried out in accordance with classical ichthyological methods.

The fish were measured with an ichthyometer with an accuracy of 1 mm (total length = TL)(figure 4), weighed with a scale with an accuracy of 1 g (TW)(figure 5), and to determine the age, 10 - 20 scales were collected from the area between the lateral and dorsal lines.

Age determination was done by reading the annual growth rings on the scales using a binocular microscope.

Figure 4. Specimens of Danube shad caught in experimental fishing

Figure 5. Body weight recording of Danube shad

Monitoring of physical, chemical and hydrobiological parameters

Water quality monitoring and management, dissolved oxygen, pH and water temperature were measured at each fish collection point. Dissolved oxygen and temperature were measured using a HACH HQ 40d oximeter; pH was measured with a WTW pH meter (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Recording of water hydrochemical parameters

Figure 7. Water sample collection for hydrobiology analyses

The environmental conditions were determined by physicochemical and hydrobiological analyses carried out by taking water samples (figure 7) which were subsequently processed in the laboratory. The determination of the main hydrochemical parameters was carried out by known methods. The hydrobiological study involved quantitative and qualitative analysis of plankton (phytoplankton and zooplankton). The values of the quality indicators were analysed and interpreted, according to order no. 161/2006 "Regulations on the classification of surface water quality in order to establish the ecological status of water bodies" approved by the Order of the Minister of Environment and Water Management .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data on hydroclimatic factors in the area of the Danube sector from Km 615 (Gârcov) to Km 863 (Iron Gates II)

The variability of hydroclimatic factors has a significant impact on the migration of Danube shad in the Danube River. Changes in the hydrological and climatic regime, caused by both natural and human factors, can disrupt the migratory cycle of the species and have negative consequences on the shad population.

Table no. 2. Average and extreme monthly flows on the Danube at the entrance to the country (February - July 2025)

Flow rates (Q)	February 2025		March 2025		April 2025		May 2025		June 2025		July 2025	
	m.a.		m.a.		m.a.		m.a.		m.a.		m.a.	
Maximum Q (mc/s)		4800		7000		9000		7000		7500		6000
Average Q (mc/s)	5300	3700	6700	5000	7900	7000	7250	5100	6400	6000	5350	4700
Minimum Q (mc/s)		3000		3000		5500		4200		3800		3500

The implementation of appropriate habitat conservation and management measures, as well as careful monitoring of Danube shad populations, is essential to protect the migration and ensure the ecological stability of the Danube River.

According to the National Institute of Hydrology and Water Management (INHGA), based on medium and long-term statistical elements, the forecast of average and extreme monthly flows on the Danube at the entrance to the country (Baziaş section) was developed for the period February - July 2025, values presented in table no. 2 [9].

Also, in the table, in the column "m.a." are presented the multiannual average values of the flows corresponding to the months: February, March, April, May, June and July.

According to the National Institute of Hydrology and Water Management (INHGA), the prognostic estimates for the months of February - July 2025 for the studied sector, in the vast majority of cases, the values were within the range of 30 - 80% of the normal monthly values.

Presentation and interpretation of data from the water analysis bulletin at Corabia point (km 640 and km 648)

Tables 3 and 4 present the analysis reports of water samples from the Danube in the Corabia area (km 640 and km 648).

Table no. 3. Analysis bulletin – (water sample, Corabia collection point)

<i>Recorded parameters</i>		<i>Station 1</i>	<i>Station 2</i>
Dissolved oxygen (mg/l)		8.72	9.04
Saturation (%)		94.3	91.1
Water temperature (°C)	Area (0.5 m)	18.7	18.8
	Depth (3 m)	18.4	18.2

Following the hydrochemical analyses of the samples (**Corabia km 640 and Corbia km 648**), increases/decreases in some parameters that play a role in maintaining the buffering capacity of the water and maintaining a physiological state within the normal range of fish were highlighted.

Table no. 4. Values of water sample analysis report from Corabia collection point compared to values according to MMGA Order 161/2005

FEATURES	M.U.	Sample analyzed 1	Sample analyzed 2	Values according to Ordinance MMGA 161/2006		
				Minimum	Optimum	Maximal
Temperature	°C	18.7	18.8			
pH		7.2	7.2	6.9	7 - 7.8	8 - 8.5
Total hardness	dGH	5.04	5.10	5	12	20
Alkalinity HCl 0.1 N	ml	3.0 + 0	3.12 + 0	0.2	2.0 - 4.0	8
HCO ₃ ⁻	mg/l	183.0	190.3	20 -100	200 - 400	600
CO ₃ ²⁻	mg/l	-	-	-	traces	10.0 - 20.0
Calcium Ca ²⁺	mg/l	23.6	24.4	30	90 -120	160

Magnesium Mg ²⁺	mg/l	7.53	7.29	6	10.0 - 40.0	50.0	
Ca ²⁺ / Mg ²⁺	mg/l	3.13	3.34	2	5	10	
Oxidability KMnO ₄	mg/l	11.36	11.98	5	20	60	
O ₂ -CCO (Mn)	mg/l	2.88	3.03	6	7.0 - 12.0	14.0	
P from PO ₄ ³⁺	mg/l	0.488	0.502	0.005	0.05 - 1.5	3	
N from NO ₃ ⁻	mg/l	0.324	0.346	1	2.5 - 4	30	
N from NO ₂ ⁻	mg/l	0.018	0.020	lack	0.03	0.06	
Chloride	Cl ⁻	mg/l	2.12	2.47	6	30	40
	NaCl	mg/l	3.50	4.09	15	20	30
Ammonium NH ₄ ⁺	mg/l	0	0	0.05 - 0.5	0.5 - 1	2	

Monitoring of hydrobiological parameters of Danube water in the area of Corabia km 640 and Corabia km 648

Qualitative and quantitative structure of phytoplankton in the analyzed samples

Following the analysis of water samples from the two areas, a number of 20 species belonging to 3 taxonomic groups were identified, namely: diatoms 13 species, chlorophyceae 5 species and cyanophyceae 3 species. The development of algae in rivers is limited by water currents, most often the appearance of a substantial biomass being attributed to tributaries and sources, such as lakes in their watershed. The numerical density was between 28580 ex/l and 78450 ex/l.

The dominance, in terms of specific diversity, belongs to the *Bacillariophyta* group, representing 54.3% of the total number of identified species, followed by the *Chlorophyceae* group with 23.8% and *Euglenophyceae* with 21.8%.

In the Corabia km 640 area, a number of 19 species belonging to a number of 5 taxonomic groups were highlighted, namely: diatoms 10 species, chlorophyceae 3 species, cyanophyceae 3 species, cryptophyceae 2 species and dinophyceae 1 species. As for the weight. This belongs to the *Bacillariophyta* group with 41.2% of the total species identified, followed by *Chlorophyta* with 26.9%, *Chryptophyta* with 24.4%, *Cyanophyta* 6.4% and *Dinophyta* 1.1% (fig. no. 8). The numerical density was between 68450 ex/l – 78480 ex/l. The phytoplankton biomass was between 18.3 mg/l and 20.9 mg/l.

In the Corabia km 648 area, a number of 14 species belonging to a number of 5 taxonomic groups were identified, namely: diatoms 9 species, chlorophyceae 1 species, cyanophyceae 2 species, cryptophyceae 1 species and dinophyceae 1 species. In terms of weight, this belongs to the *Bacillariophyta* group with 60.4% of the total identified species, followed by *Chlorophyta* with 22.1%, *Chryptophyta* with 10.6%, *Cyanophyta* 6.0% and *Dinophyta* 0.9% (fig. no. 8). The numerical density was between 55380 ex/l – 81350 ex/l. The phytoplankton biomass was between 12.6 mg/l and 18.4 mg/l.

Zooplankton analysis- Research conducted on the qualitative and quantitative composition of zooplankton has highlighted the existence of three systematic groups represented by 17 taxa.

Corabia km 640 zooplankton analysis showed the presence of 18 taxa. The systematic group Rotifera is represented by 12 species, *Copepoda* by 3 species and *Cladocera* by 3 species. The highest share value was obtained by the taxonomic group *Rotifera* (70.5%), followed by the *Copepoda* group (22.3%) and *Cladocera* (7.2%) (fig. no. 9). Regarding the numerical density we can say that: rotifers recorded an average value of 255 ex/l, cladocerans 82 ex/l and copepods 124 ex/l. The total zooplankton biomass recorded for the 3 taxonomic groups was between 1.80 g/m³ - 2.30 g/m³.

Corabia km 648 zooplankton analysis showed the presence of 17 taxa. The systematic group Rotifera is represented by 11 species, *Copepoda* by 3 species and *Cladocera* by 3 species. The highest share value was obtained by the taxonomic group *Rotifera* (72.7%), followed by the *Copepoda* group (20.8%) and *Cladocera* (6.5%) (fig. no. 9). Regarding the numerical density we can say that: rotifers recorded an average value of 232 ex/l, cladocerans 96 ex/l and copepods 135 ex/l. The total zooplankton biomass recorded for the 3 taxonomic groups was between 1.60 g/m³ - 2.62 g/m³.

Data on research conducted in 2025 on the migration of Danube shad (*Alosa immacuata*) in the sector Km 615 (Gârcov) to Km 863 (Iron Gates II)

The experimental fishing was carried out with nets with and without gillnets and aimed to achieve the following objectives:

- determining the number of fish caught;
- determining the age of fished specimens by reading the annual growth rings on the scales;
- sex determination;
- establishing body mass (g/ex) and body length (Lt.- cm);
- establishing the prolificity and maturation stage of females.

Figure 8. Phytoplankton dynamics in the analyzed areas

Figure 9. Zooplankton dynamics in the analyzed areas

Table no. 5. Total number of captured specimens and sex ratio of Danube shad

No. crt.	Capture	Ex.	%
1.	Specimens (♂)	106	51.0
2.	Specimens (♀)	102	49.0
3.	Total	208	100.0

According to the data presented in tables 5 and 6, the following aspects are highlighted, namely:

- the total number of Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) specimens resulting from the experimental fish are 208 specimens, of which 106 specimens are males (♂) and 102 specimens are females (♀);
- by age, total captured specimens, of which males (♂) and females (♀) are:
 - 2 years: 14 individuals, of which 8 males (♂) and 6 females (♀);
 - 3 years: 96 individuals, of which 52 males (♂) and 44 females (♀);
 - 4 years: 80 individuals, of which 37 males (♂) and 43 females (♀);
 - 5 years: 18 individuals, of which 9 males (♂) and 9 females (♀);
- in terms of age, out of the total number of Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) specimens captured, the predominant ones are those aged 3 years (96 individuals/52♂+44♀), respectively 4 years (80 individuals/37♂+43♀).

Table no. 6. Data on the number of Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) specimens captured and data on age, sex ratio, total length (Lt.- cm), average weight (W- g/ex) determined on the fish material harvested (♂/♀) + (♀)

Specifications	Stock				Total/limits
	2	3	4	5	
Age in years	2	3	4	5	
Number of exemplars	14	96	80	18	208
Sex ratio (♂/♀)	8/6	52/44	37/43	9/9	106/102
Total length (Lt.) - cm (♂ + ♀) - average/year	25.0/27.8/ 26.4	30.0/32.4/ 31.2	32.5/36.5/ 34.5	35.0/38.2/ 36.5	26.4- 36.5
Total length (Lt.) - cm (♀) - limits/average	26.1 - 29.5/ 27.8	30.8 - 34.1/ 32.4	34.6 - 38.4/ 36.5	37.2 - 39.0/ 38.1	27.8 - 38.1
Average weight (W.) - g/ex (♂ + ♀)	128/136 /132	251/266/ 256	294/311/ 303	343/358/ 351	132- 351
Average weight (W.) - g/ex (♀) limits/average	128 - 144/ 136	258 - 274/ 266	296 - 326/ 311	351 - 365/ 358	136 - 358

Following biometric measurements that determined total length (Lt. – cm) and body mass (W - g/ex), the following data were recorded:

- the total length (Lt. – cm) as a general average value measured for all specimens of Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*), males (106 ♂) and females (102 ♀) at all ages is within the range of 26.4 – 36.5 cm, and the body mass (W- g/ex) within the range of 132 – 351 g/ex;
- both in terms of total length (Lt. – cm) and body mass (W – g/ex), the values of these parameters are lower in males, regardless of age;

In female specimens (♀), the following average values for each age of the two biometric parameters (Lt. – cm and W. – g/ex) were determined and from the data in the table the following values are recorded:

- for all four ages, the total length value (Lt. – cm) is between 27.8 cm (2-year-old female) and 38.1 cm (5-year-old female), the parameter values increase with age.
- for all four ages, the body mass value (W. – g/ex) increases with age and is between 136 g/ex (2-year-old female) and 358 g/ex (5-year-old female).

Data on the degree of maturation and prolificity of Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) spawners in the Danube sector km 615 (Gârcov) to km 863 (Iron Gates II)

To determine the stage of gonadal development, a number of 50 females (♀) were studied, only those aged 3 and 4 years, respectively, which were numerically predominant in the shad batches captured, 25 from each age group (25 3-year-old ♀ out of 44 captured and 25 4-year-old ♀ out of 43 captured).

From the data presented in table no. 7 it results that of the females studied both for the two ages (3 years, 4 years) and for the two ages taken together, the specimens in the IV - V stage of maturation predominate (25 ♀ /11 ex ♀ -3 years /14 ex ♀ -4 years) and grade IV (13 ex ♀/7 ex ♀ - 3 years - 6 years/16 ex ♀ - 4 years). Stage III – IV of gonadal development was identified in a number of 5 ex females, of which 3 ex ♀ aged 3 years and 2 ex ♀ aged 4 years, and grade V in 7 ex ♀ (4 ex ♀ aged 3 years and 3 ex ♀ aged 4 years).

Female Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) aged 2 years (6 ex ♀) and 5 years (9 ex ♀) were not studied to determine the degree of gonadal maturation due to the low number of specimens captured.

Table no. 7. Degree of gonadal development in female Danube shad fished in the Danube sector km 615 (Gârcov) to km 863 (Iron Gates II)

<i>Specification</i>	<i>Stages of gonadal development</i>					
Number of females ♀(ex)	III	III - IV	IV	IV - V	V	Total ♀
Age	3 years					
-		3	7	11	4	25
Age	4 years					
-		2	6	14	3	25
<i>Recapitulation</i>						
Age	3 + 4 years					
Total	-	5	13	25	7	50

From the point of view of the degree of gonadal development determined in 3-year-old and 4-year-old specimens, it results that all female Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) captured in the Danube sector studied, namely the area between km 615 (Gârcov) and km 863 (Iron Gates II), were ready for reproduction (spawning) according to sexual maturity defined by the degree of gonadal development.

The examination of males regarding reproductive capacity revealed the certainty that approximately 95% of the total specimens examined (10 specimens from the two predominant age groups (3 + 4 years) were ready for reproduction (sperm release), the stage of gonadal development being evaluated at IV and V, respectively.

Data on the gonosomatic ratio in female Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) in the Danube sector km 615 (Gârcov) to km 863 (Iron Gates II)

The gonosomatic ratio (maturity index) in Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) is directly dependent on the stage of gonadal development (table 8), the highest average value of the gonosomatic ratio is recorded in females, regardless of age, in stage IV (15.84), 10.38 (stage III – IV), 10.30 (stage IV – V) and 9.31 (stage V).

Table no. 8. Average values and limits of variation of the gonosomatic ratio for the two age groups (3 + 4 years) in female Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*)

Age (♀)	Stage	No. of exemplars	Gonosomatic ratio (average values)	
			Average	Variation limits
3 + 4 years	III - IV	5	10,38	7,75 - 13,00
	IV	13	15,84	13,55 - 18,13
	IV - V	25	10,30	8,53 - 12,06
	V	7	9,31	8,68 - 9,93
Total/ averages		50	-	7,75 - 18,13

Results obtained regarding the prolificity of Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) in the Danube sector km 615 (Gârcov) to km 863 (Iron Gates II)

To determine the prolificity of the Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*), egg samples were taken from 22 female specimens (♀) aged 3 years, of which 7 ex(♀) with stage IV of gonadal development, 11 ex(♀) with stage IV - V and 4 (♀) with stage V and from 23 ex(♀) 4-year-old females, of which 6 ex(♀) with stage IV of gonadal development, 14 ex(♀) with stage IV - V and 3 ex(♀) with stage V (table 9).

Table no. 9. Values of the number of eggs/gram determined in female Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) depending on age, stage of gonadal development and egg category

Age (years)	Development stage of gonads	No. of exemplars	Number of eggs/gram			
			Category I		Category II	
			Averag	Limts	Average	Limts
3	IV	7	2.120	1.850 - 2.390	2.052	1.354 - 2.750
	IV - V	11	2.574	2.240 - 2.908	1.845	1.020 - 2.670
	V	4	1.120	966 - 1.274	1.032	912 - 1.152
Total/limits		22	-	966 - 2.908	-	912 - 2.750
4	IV	6	2.462	2.021 - 2.903	1.750	1.706 - 1.794
	IV - V	14	2.548	2.248 - 2.848	1.894	1.466 - 2.322
	V	3	1.830	1.686 - 1.974	1.550	1.300 - 1.800
Total/limits		23	-	1686 - 2.903	-	1.300 - 2.322

Depending on the stage of development of the gonads and the size category of the eggs (category I and category II), the number of eggs per female (♀) and the number of eggs per 1 g of eggs were determined;

The data regarding the number of eggs/gram show that the highest number was determined in females whose eggs are in the IV - V degree of gonadal development for both 3-year-old and 4-year-old specimens, for both categories of eggs;

- the average values of the number of eggs/g are 2,574 eggs/g for category I eggs and 1,845 eggs/g for category II eggs in 3-year-old females;

- in 4-year-old females, the number of eggs/g data reveals the same aspect, the number of eggs/g is higher in stage IV - V of gonadal development for both categories of eggs (2,548 eggs/g/category I, respectively 1,894 eggs/g/category II);
- as with the number of eggs/female (♀) and the number of eggs/gram, there is an increase in the number of eggs/gram in relation not only to age, but also to the passage of the gonads from stage IV (average 2,361) to stage IV - V (average 2,731), then a decrease in the number of eggs/gram in females with stage V of gonad development (average 1,246);

CONCLUSIONS

As a result of the experimental fishing carried out in the Danube sector km 615 (Gârcov) to km 863 (Iron Gates II) in May, a number of 208 specimens of Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*) were captured, of which 106 males (♂) and 102 females (♀), grouped into four age categories: 2, 3, 4 and 5 years respectively;

- in terms of age, both females and males were dominated by 3-year-old specimens (96 ex – 52 ex♂ + 44 ex♀), respectively 4-year-old specimens (80 ex – 37 ex♂ + 43 ex♀);

- as a result of biometric measurements that involved determining total length Lt (cm) and average weight W (g/ex), 3 value classes were established for the Lt indicator and four for the W indicator.

- regardless of age, stage or size, eggs of different sizes (categories) were identified in the gonads of Danube shad (*Alosa immaculata*), which certifies that spawning occurs in portions;

- the shad specimens that make up the schools within the studied sector are mostly with gonads in stages IV and IV - V and fewer in stages III - V and V;

- following the data of the prolificity parameters, a gradual increase is observed in both the number of eggs/♀ and the number of eggs/g (average values and variation limits), in relation not only to age, but also to the passage of the gonads from stage IV to stage IV - V of gonad development.

The relatively "stable" situation of natural variation in the size of shad populations can be a trap in the conservation and sustainable exploitation of stocks because some negative environmental and overexploitation effects can manifest themselves many years after the phenomena have occurred.

Currently, there is a need to correlate environmental regulations with exploitation regulations to ensure sustainable management of shad stocks, in the context of pressures generated by the presence of the Iron Gates II dam, overfishing and climate change.

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